

Floods in Southern Suburbs of Athens (January 2026)

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Description of the event – main findings

On the afternoon of 21 January 2026, local flash flooding occurred in the southern suburbs of Athens due to heavy rainfall, mainly during the afternoon hours. Parts of eastern Attica and the easternmost areas of the Athens basin received up to 170 mm of rain in less than 24 hours, and specifically in less than 18 hours (**Figure 1**). However, much of this rainfall fell in less than 2 hours (**Figures 2 and 4**). It is also worth noting that instantaneous rainfall intensities of up to 250–300 mm per hour (mm/h) were recorded in the afternoon, highlighting how extreme the rainfall was (**Figure 1**).

For this analysis, data from 76 stations across the wider Attica region were used, as well as from two water level sensors, one on the Kifisos River (**Figure 2**) and one on the Pikrodafni stream (**Figure 4**). All meteorological data are recorded at intervals of 1 to 10 minutes, depending on the type of station and the quality of the communications network used by the stations to transmit the data. The water level data were recorded by radar sensors every 15 minutes from an experimental network that is operated in collaboration with the Department of Inland Waters of the Hellenic Centre for Marine Research.

Figure 1. Total rainfall as recorded by the WeatherXM network stations (left), and a snapshot of instantaneous rainfall intensities at the time a strong storm cell entered the southernmost parts of the city (right). The interpolation was performed using the IDW method. The drainage (stream) network is shown with white lines.

In the Kifisos stream, the water level appears to have risen gradually during the first phase of the storm. In particular, a small local rise in the water level of about 30 cm appears to have been caused by a short and sharp increase in rainfall intensity (around 40 mm/h) in the far northern part of the city (Agios Stefanos) (**Figure 2**). Later, a second and much stronger peak in rainfall intensity in the southern areas, which exceeded 150 mm/h locally, caused a sudden rise in the

Kifisos water level by more than 1.5 meters. The peak of the water level was observed around 18:20 and the duration of this water level rise was approximately one hour. Overall, the main volume of water that raised the river level appears to have come from the rainfall that fell in the central and southern parts of the city, rather than from runoff coming from the upstream areas.

Figure 2. Rain rate (in mm/h) as recorded by 5 WeatherXM stations and water level of the Kifisos stream (in m) (top). Cumulative daily rain (in mm) recorded by the same stations along the Kifisos stream (middle). Map with the locations of the stations where the Kifisos and Pikrodafni streams are indicated by the yellow lines (below).

The above information is in line with the rainfall return periods that varied significantly during the event at both temporal and spatial scales. In particular, at Kifisos Nikaia water level monitoring site, the existing meteorological station recorded rainfall return periods of more than 600 years for rainfall duration of 1 hour while the return periods decreased significantly for larger durations. In other parts of the city the rainfall return periods were significantly lower for the entire event since both the cumulative rainfall and rainfall intensities were much lower in comparison to the central-north part of Attica region (**Figure 3**).

Figure 3. Rainfall return periods during the event of 21/01/2026 as estimated by rainfall data for: a) Kifisos-Nikaia HCMR's water and meteorological station (based on the ombrian curves of Piraeus meteorological station) and b) Argyroupoli HCMR's monitoring site (based on the ombrian curves of Ilioupoli meteorological station).

Regarding the Pikrodafni stream and the surrounding area, the main volume of rainfall occurred (with the highest intensity) between 17:00 and 19:00, with instantaneous rainfall rates reaching up to 270 mm/h (for example in the Agios Dimitrios / Vyronas area). This was the event that raised the water level of the Pikrodafni stream by about 1.5 meter within 2 hours which marginally did not affect the surrounding areas (**Figure 4**).

Figure 4. Rain rate (in mm/h) as recorded by 4 WeatherXM stations and water level of the Pikrodafni stream zeroed at 00:00 21/012026 for clarity (in m) (top). Cumulative daily rain (in mm) recorded by the

same stations along the Pirkodafni stream (middle). Map with the locations of the stations where the Pirkodafni stream is indicated by the yellow line (below).

Figure 5. Accumulated precipitation in Ano Glyfada at the event of 21/01/2026 and various relevant forecasts from well-known meteorological models.

Finally, regarding the forecasts produced by different models 24–48 hours before the storm, there was a very large spread in the predicted total rainfall, ranging from 40 mm to 100 mm for the area that flooded on the afternoon of 21 January 2026 (Antheon Street, Ano Glyfada). The ICON and WeatherXM’s MOSAIC models were closer to what was ultimately recorded by the station (**Figure 5**). The use of machine learning models is a very promising methodology, which the Department of Inland Waters of HCMR has already begun to implement in the Pinios River basin.

The above analysis illustrates the necessity of meteorological and water level data in a dense spatial scale to allow the establishment of effective early warning systems and provide the essential information for understanding the extreme weather events and designing appropriate flood mitigation strategies.

The data of this analysis (see attached files in this publication) originate from the WeatherXM meteorological stations network (<https://weatherxm.com/>) while the water level data come from the Department of Inland Waters-HCMR network (<https://hydro-stations.hcmr.gr/>).